

Workforce Diversity and Employee Performance in National Museum of Kenya

Obinge Francis Oyoo ^{1*}, Dr. Elizabeth Nambuswa Makokha (Phd) ^{1,2}

¹College of Human Resource Development, Department of Entrepreneurship and Procurement Leadership and Management. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, P.O. Box 62000 - 00200, Nairobi Kenya

²College of Human Resource Development, Department of Entrepreneurship and Procurement Leadership and Management. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, P.O. Box 62000 - 00200, Nairobi Kenya

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13341918>

Published Date: 19-August-2024

Abstract: The purpose of the study was to establish the effect of workforce diversity on employee performance at National Museum of Kenya. The study was guided by the following study objective; to determine the effect of ethnicity diversity on employee performance at National Museum of Kenya. The study was underpinned by the following theories Primordia list approach to ethnicity theory. The study employed a descriptive study design. The target population of 552 and sample size of 232 respondents were included, that is senior management middle level management, support management and hospitality. The data collection instruments was questionnaires. Multiple regression was used to test the significance levels of one variable over the other. Analysis of variance was also used. The presentation of the quantitative data from the coded closed ended questions was tabulated using tables, charts, graphs with aid of SPSS software. From the results, there was a very strong relationship between ethnicity diversity and employee performance at National Museum of Kenya ($r = .896$, p value $=0.002$). The relationship was significant since the p value 0.002 was less than 0.05 (significant level). The study came up with the following recommendations; the management of National Museum of Kenya should try to embrace a culture which is not discriminative to enable high performance and also encourage customs and culture beliefs that dictate how employees relate with other colleagues and do work with. National Management of Kenya should discourage the employees from indulging in ethnic differences as they are likely to disrupt peace and harmony existing amongst the employees in this organization. The management should hire and recruit employees from all ethnic backgrounds from all over the country hence leads to increased productivity. The management should come up with specific training approaches to enable a workforce full of specific skills, knowledge, attitudinal or task information to enable employee performance.

Keywords: Ethnicity Diversity, Organisational performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Organisations with a diverse workforce are better equipped to serve various external consumers in an increasingly global market. Such organisations better understand the legal, financial, educational, economic, and cultural requirements (Thanseer et al., 2020). A study by Benton and Walker (2018) demonstrated that some organisations have successfully implemented programs and policies that foster diversity and inclusiveness in the workplace. Organisations that advance and accomplish a diverse working environment will draw in and retain quality representatives and increase customer loyalty. The result shows that workplace diversity has contributed to more productivity, but some factors, such as differential treatment, could hinder its successful implementation and company success (Dike, 2013). Successful management of our increasingly diverse workforce is one of the most important challenges facing organizations today (Mor Brak, 2012). According to Wambui *et al.*, (2013), by managing diversity, companies interact with different cultures and clients. However, recent studies have indicated that on a global scenario, most of the countries organization' have not actually considered work force

diversity management have taken place in America, in Europe and also in South Africa (Kamenou, 2007; Wambui, 2013). For instance, the study of diversity management, a concept which originated in the USA before travelling to Europe and now finally to Africa, clearly shows that the institutional environment, culture, governing regulations and social norms all greatly influence the form which diversity management and accompanying measures assume in a certain context (Mensiklarbach *et al.*, (2013).

A research by Wambari (2013) indicates that diversity management developed after several decades of US minority policies of affirmative action (AA) and equal employment opportunity (EEO) whose main aim was to rectify past discrimination and to prevent future discrimination in employment. Regarding the European Union the situation is even more complex, as diverse societies and cultures are located within the EU's borders (Mensi-klarbach, 2014). Thus, although they share similar pillars regarding antidiscrimination, European countries are culturally diverse, and therefore tackle the issue of diversity rather differently. In Pakistan, Khan, Sohali, Uddin and Sufyan (2019) indicated that gender, experience and ethnic diversity had a significant influence on the performance of employees in various organizations including the educational sector.

In Africa, ethnicity and tribes seem to be the main factors within the regulative system (Fitzgerald, 2010). In spite of this, with the changing demographic composition of the workforce, managing diversity in organizations has become an important organizational function (Olsen & Luis, 2012). Organizations have employed varying approaches to diversity management, resulting in varying organizations outcomes (Olsen & Luis, 2012). In Africa for example, ethnic discrimination and prejudice lead to talent wastage when organizations refuse to hire applicants because of the unfavorable hold of people from such ethnic groups. On the contrary, Chinese and Africa cultures in managing HR activities like hiring, promoting, rewarding, and dismissal in orders to influence employee job satisfaction in host country in Africa (Nyambegera, Kamoche, Siebers, 2016). Nyambegera (2002) therefore argues that Africa organizations needs to move away from approaches of exclusion and embrace the inclusion of those qualified regardless of ethnic affiliation in order to utilize effectively the resource behind organizational effectiveness in its workforce.

In South Africa for instance, diversity communication and training have since become the recent phenomena owing to the historical lack of workforce diversity in most of the workplaces. According to Madera and Kapoor (2011) however, since 1994 there have been new laws introduced around the areas of employment equity, affirmative action and Black Economic Empowerment (BEE). Few of such studies that exist, have not deliver detailed examination of what workforce diversity is. Most of the previous studies on diversity management issues are conducted in developed countries, especially in Western perspectives like America and Europe. This study will focus on developing continent, Africa. The African government is facing many challenges from human resource management perspective, which ends up in negative growth of its government operations (Wong & Li, 2015). Studies supported the African governments have revealed that there is an absence of qualified subordinates and managerial employees due to low staff diversity (Ouko, 2004; Musamba, 2019).

According to Parboteeah, Seriki and Hoegl (2014), Ethnicity is a sensitive political issue in sub-Saharan Africa. It lies at the hearty of African diversity and has been found to impinge heavily on the workplace. In Kenya for example, workforce diversity management has not been clearly observed in most of the organizations around the country. This could be due to Kenya's long and troubled history as a crown colony, including the fight for independence and violent conflict to gain equal opportunities; issues of diversity are fundamentally linked with antidiscrimination and equal rights (Hanappi-Edger & Ukur, 2011). However, with its cultural difference, the nation is struggling to live up to high democratic ideals within the context of this diversity (Frances, Hino, Lonsdale & Ranis, 2013).

Unfortunately, regarding representation in the civil service, it has been observed that some departments in Kenyan organizations are exclusively staffed by one particular ethnic group, and that frequently, individuals can only secure a position if they are supported by another person who could either bring their case to the relevant authority or make the decision himself or herself (Nyambegera, 2002). According to Maingi (2015), workforce diversity is a major challenge that has turned into a losing situation for all involved, leading to demoralization of employees thus affecting employees' performance in many organizations. In tandem with then above, a study done by the Public Service Commission indicated that of the 236231 employees in the public sector as at June 30, 2013, Kenyan three ethnic communities accounted for 49 percent which literally translated to 115 633 of the total workforce. This shows therefore that the remaining 120,598 (representing 51 percent) employees are from the remaining 39 communities.

In light of this, a survey done by LEFTIE (2011) indicated that Kenya is facing a crisis of tribalism. This is whereby after the first ethnic audit of the civil service, it was revealed that there are five big communities within the country which occupy nearly 70 percent of all jobs in the public sector.

Evidently from the report, the problem of diversity management in the workforce is not properly addressed in the Kenya civil service. For this reason, the civil service (CS), as the principle instrument of the state has inevitably attracted renewed attention (Olowu, 2014). Efforts are underway, for example, in order to address the problems of institutionalized ethnic discrimination, Kenya enacted a new constitution in 2010 to replace the independence constitution of 1963. In addition, the Kenyan public sector is undergoing a drastic transformation to present itself as an equal and fair employer in line with the constitutional requirements, similarly the human resource management of the public service aims to address and eliminate imbalances (Tshikwatamwa, 2013). In spite of these efforts, Jones and George (2011) state that managers face many challenges in effectively managing diversity. They further argue that each kind of diversity present managers with particular issues they need to appreciate. Conclusively, Munjuri (2012) suggests that some diversity management strategies such as emphasis on team work fosters better relationships within a department and can promote identity within the department or organization that moves beyond service level differences. Other strategies considered to influence employees' performance in this research include, Diversity policies, Diversity training programs, Work teams, Affirmative action and Diversity committees.

Workforce diversity management is considered one of the main challenges for human resource management in modern organizations (Martin, Miguel, Pedro & Sanchez, 2013). Workforce diversity is a complex phenomenon to manage in an organization. The management of workforce diversity as a tool to increase organizational effectiveness cannot be underscored, especially with current changes sweeping across the globe. Owing to this, there is need to investigate the awareness of managers on certain skills necessary for the creation of a diverse workforce environment. Employee performance is how well an employee is effectively fulfilling his/ her job requirement or discharging his/ her duties so as to achieve good results (Durga, 2017). Armstrong (2012) citing Vroom (1994) said performance or effectiveness is a function of ability and motivation. Thus, employees need both ability and motivation for effective performance. NMK has not performed to the expectations in terms of service delivery to its customers (Kamau, 2017). A study by Ouma (2013) on diversity and performance in NMK, Matuga revealed that service delivery and efficiencies of operations was low. Tanui, 2017 in the study of NMK revealed that there is ineffective, inefficient and inexperienced employees and managerial incompetence at the institution. In recent years, most organizations have embraced workforce diversity with an aim to increase profits and productivity. This integration has perhaps been done hurriedly, eyeing the end result and not actually understanding the steps that should be followed. This has resulted in management that is not skilled enough to control and manage workforce diversity, and its ethics such as battling discrimination, fostering inclusiveness, acknowledging the value of diversity, dealing with losses due to prejudice as well as complaints or legal actions against the organizations (Devoe, 2014).

Diversified workforce is the latest and current trend in every organization today. Moreover, the major concern for every organization is to enhance its productivity because organizations are an economic activity and can only stay afloat by competing in this cutthroat competitive world by generating more profits. Due to the diversified workforce, people are facing a lot more problems at the workplace. There is less collaboration and teamwork from some colleagues. However in order to achieve the organizational goals all members must be effective in terms of the roles they perform within the department. To those who are not very cooperative, firing is not the solution, which is what most managers have been doing. Bedi *et al.*, (2014) indicates some of the consequences of ignoring diversity in an organization is unhealthy tensions between individuals of different culture or race, loss of productivity as a result in increased conflict and inability to retain talented employees. He further adds that good management alone does not necessarily ensure good diversity management. Several managers in organization have always thought being good managers or bosses sets the example of creating friendliness in the office. As a result, poor diversity management has been tolerated in the office, without the management knowing the core problem and consequently, no solution has been formulated.

A number of research studies have been conducted in Kenya's private sector on work diversity in relation to work diversity management strategies and organizational performance. However, none of these has focused on the effect of workforce diversity on employee performance (Munjuri & Maina 2013 and (Oluoch, 2006) addressed the issue of workforce diversity management practices. None of the above studies focused on workforce diversity management in the public institutions. Therefore, the study sought to determine the effect of ethnicity diversity on employee performance at National Museum of Kenya.

2. ETHNICITY DIVERSITY

With the advent of globalization in the 21st century, increased mobility of labour around the world has been evidenced which necessitated another form of public sector reform which is aimed at enhancing service delivery of public sector institutions. This reform was centred on workforce diversity, (Gaio & Gonçalves, 2022). Perhaps the earliest study on record that examined ethnicity and work-related outcomes was conducted in 1958. Katz et al. studied the interpersonal relations between blacks and whites in a laboratory study comprised of 18 four-person teams. Each team included two white students and two black students. The study used open and positive communication as the outcome of interest. Not surprisingly, white students were more likely than blacks to communicate, and when they did communicate, they tended to direct their comments to each other, not to the black students in their team. These results likely reflect the status differences between blacks and whites during the 1950s, something that makes any older study relating ethnicity to work-related outcomes questionable. Other early studies (Hoffman et al., 1962; Hoffman & Maier, 1961; Levy, 1964) suffer from the same generalizability issue. When considering a diversity dimension like ethnicity that is so politically- and socially-charged, it is important to consider the social context when determining whether any given study remains relevant.

It is argued that organizations that value diversity will definitely cultivate success and have a future in this dynamic global labour market Wilson and Leaper, (2022). Ellis and Sonnenfeld (1994) argued that there is a relationship between a positive diversity climate, job satisfaction and commitment to the organization. There is a chance that diversity management can improve an employee's self-esteem and feeling of belongingness to the organization; this management has amplified effect on employees from minority background and there is likely that they might feel left out within the organization. To effectively manage diversity, an organization must change its approach, technique and style to prioritize diversity management as an essential organizational process (Gilbert, 1999).

Diversity management provides a way in which organization can understand unique traits and attitude of people of different group and location and therefore meet their customer needs (Hall & Parker, 1993). Diversity management initiatives maximize the potential of all employees in direct benefit to the organization. Due to the fact that employee can understand how its outcome could be desirable, so that they will support the organization's effort at managing diversity and embrace a culture that support diversity (Carrel, 2006). It is argued that organizations that value diversity will definitely cultivate success and have a future in this dynamic global labour market Wilson and Leaper, (2022). Lu et al., (2018) asserts that the capacity of an organization to leverage essential resources and implement methods to attain its goals within an organization requires understanding to perform effectively in terms of decision making, building organizational support, raising accountability and enhancing a researcher understanding. The primordial approach by saying ethnicity is a primordial attachment (Geertz, 1963; Greeley, 1974; Isaacs, 1975; Gordon, 1978) fails to recognize the relationship between ethnicity and wider social relations thus cannot explain ethnic variability. As we shall see in what follows, these problems necessitate us to examine ethnicity from a different angle which means a different conceptual framework. The primordial approach argues that ethnicity, being a given fact of human nature, is fixed and involuntary phenomena. Thus there is no place for explaining ethnic variability in the primordialist approach.

3. METHOD

The study used descriptive research design. The population involved the total 552 employees of National Museum of Kenya. The study used stratified sampling method to select a pattern that represents the entire population. Therefore, with the help of the formula, a sample of 232 was used for this study. Questionnaires were the main instruments of data collection used in this research project. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. After all the data is collected, data cleaning was done in order to determine inaccurate, incomplete, or unreasonable data and then improve the quality through correction of detected errors and omissions. The data collected was analyzed mainly by use of quantitative and qualitative techniques and presented in tables and figures. Descriptive analysis was used to determine the proportions and frequency of the variables. Multiple regression analysis model to show the link between dependent and independent variables, the statistical summaries of the result were presented in the form of percentage and tables using computer data analysis package such as the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS)

4. DISCUSSIONS

The specific objective of the study was to determine the effect of ethnicity diversity on employee performance at National Museum of Kenya. The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement on statements relating to the effect of ethnicity diversity on employee performance at National Museum of Kenya. A 5 point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in Table 4.1

From the results, the respondents agreed that the customs and culture beliefs dictate how employees relate with other colleagues and do work with here at National Museum of Kenya. This is supported by a mean of 3.942 (std. dv = 0.938). In addition, as shown by a mean of 4.722 (std. dv = 0.936), the respondents agreed that there are many conflicts within NMK employees resulting from the different languages used for communication. Further, the respondents agreed that NMK discourages the employees from indulging in ethnic differences as they are likely to disrupt peace and harmony existing amongst the employees in this organization. This is shown by a mean of 4.835 (std. dv = 0.944).

The respondents also agreed that the National Museum of Kenya has been hires and recruits employees from all ethnic backgrounds from all over the country hence leads to increased productivity. This is shown by a mean of 3.986 (std. dv = 0.935). The respondents also agreed that good ethnicity diversity management enhances employee performance. This is shown by a mean of 3.646 (std. dv = 0.921).

Table 4.1: Effects of Ethnicity Diversity on Employee Performance

Statements on ethnicity diversity	Mean	Std. Deviation
The customs and culture beliefs dictate how employees relate with other colleagues and do work with here at NMK	3.942	0.938
There are many conflicts within NMK employees resulting from the different languages used for communication	4.722	0.936
NMK discourages the employees from indulging in ethnic differences as they are likely to disrupt peace and harmony existing amongst the employees in this organization	4.835	0.944
The National Museum of Kenya has been hires and recruits employees from all ethnic backgrounds from all over the Country hence leads to increased productivity	3.986	0.935
Good ethnicity diversity management enhances employee performance	3.646	0.921
Aggregate	3.972	0.874

4.1. Effect of Employee Performance at National Museum of Kenya

The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement on various statements relating to the effect of employee performance at National Museum of Kenya. A 5 point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in Table 4.2.

From the results, the respondents agreed that NMK employees deliver timely results as well as meeting targets assigned to them. This is supported by a mean of 4.084 (std. dv = 0.997). In addition, as shown by a mean of 3.917 (std. dv = 0.831), the respondents agreed that there is an increase in my productivity generated from working in an organization with a diverse group of employees. Further, the respondents agreed that the innovation and creativity skills have been developed from interacting with employees of diverse backgrounds. This is shown by a mean of 3.858 (std. dv = 0.563). The respondents also agreed that employees strive hard to learn as well as explore new ways of providing customers with an unforgettable customer satisfaction services in diversity management. This is shown by a mean of 3.831 (std. dv = 0.851). Lastly, the results shows that good diversity management enhances employee performance. This was supported by a mean of 3.411 (std. dv = 0.644).

Table 4.2: Effect of Employee Performance

	Mean	Std. Deviation
NMK employees deliver timely results as well as meeting targets assigned to them	4.084	0.997
There is an increase in my productivity generated from working in an organization with a diverse group of employees	3.917	0.831
The innovation and creativity skills have been developed from interacting with employees of diverse backgrounds	3.858	0.563
Employees strive hard to learn as well as explore new ways of providing customers with an unforgettable customer satisfaction services in diversity management	3.831	0.851
Good diversity management enhances employee performance	3.411	0.644
Aggregate	3.835	0.868

4.2 Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics in the current study focused on correlation and regression analysis. Correlation analysis was used to determine the strength of the relationship while regression analysis was used to determine the relationship between dependent variable (employee performance at the national museum of Kenya) and independent variables (ethnicity diversity).

4.2.1 Correlation Analysis

The present study used Pearson correlation analysis to determine the strength of association between independent variables (ethnicity diversity) and the dependent variable (employee performance at national museum of Kenya). Pearson correlation coefficient range between zero and one, where by the strength of association increase with increase in the value of the correlation coefficients. The current study employed Taylor (2018) correlation coefficient ratings where by 0.80 to 1.00 depicts a very strong relationship, 0.60 to 0.79 depicts strong, 0.40 to 0.59 depicts moderate, 0.20 to 0.39 depicts weak.

Table 4.3: Correlation Coefficients

		Employee performance	Ethnicity diversity
Employee Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	180	
Ethnicity diversity	Pearson Correlation	.896**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	180	180

From the results, there was a very strong relationship between ethnicity diversity and employee performance at National Museum of Kenya ($r = .896$, p value = 0.002). The relationship was significant since the p value 0.002 was less than 0.05 (significant level).

4.2.2 Regression Analysis

Multivariate regression analysis was used to assess the relationship between independent variables (ethnicity diversity) and the dependent variable (employee performance at National Museum of Kenya)

Table 4.4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.923	.814	.843	.20321

a. Predictors: (Constant), ethnicity diversity

The model summary was used to explain the variation in the dependent variable that could be explained by the independent variables. The r-squared for the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable was 0.814. This implied that 81.4% of the variation in the dependent variable (employee performance at National Museum of Kenya) could be explained by independent variables (ethnicity diversity).

4.2.3. ANOVA

Table 4. 5: Analysis of Variance

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	22.011	1	3.025	42.39	.000 ^b
Residual	6.516	179	.034		
Total	28.527	180			

a. Dependent Variable: employee performance at National Museum of Kenya

b. Predictors: (Constant), ethnicity diversity

The ANOVA was used to determine whether the model was a good fit for the data. F calculated was 42.39. The p value was 0.000. Therefore, the model can be used to predict the influence of ethnicity diversity on employee performance at National Museum of Kenya.

Table 4.6: Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.464	0.036		5.312	0.000
	Ethnicity diversity	0.657	0.093	0.391	3.751	0.004

a Dependent Variable: Employee Performance at National Museum of Kenya

The regression model was as follows:

$$Y = 0.464 + 0.657X_1 + \varepsilon$$

According to the results, ethnicity diversity has a significant effect on employee performance at National Museum of Kenya ($\beta_1=0.657$, p value= 0.004). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.004 was less than the significant level of 0.05.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The first specific objective of the study was to determine the effect of ethnicity diversity on employee performance at National Museum of Kenya. The findings indicated that the customs and culture beliefs dictate how employees relate with other colleagues and do work with here at National Museum of Kenya and that there are many conflicts within NMK employees resulting from the different languages used for communication. Further, the findings revealed that NMK discourages the employees from indulging in ethnic differences as they are likely to disrupt peace and harmony existing amongst the employees in this organization. The findings also showed that the National Museum of Kenya has been hires and recruits employees from all ethnic backgrounds from all over the country hence leads to increased productivity and that good ethnicity diversity management enhances employee performance.

Based on the findings, the study concluded that, ethnicity diversity has a significant effect on employee performance at National Museum of Kenya ($\beta_1=0.657$, p value= 0.004). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.004 was less than the significant level of 0.05. The study came up with the following recommendations; the management of National Museum of Kenya should try to embrace a culture which is not discriminative to enable high performance and also encourage customs and culture beliefs that dictate how employees relate with other colleagues and do work with. National Management of Kenya should discourage the employees from indulging in ethnic differences as they are likely to disrupt peace and harmony existing amongst the employees in this organization.

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